

DEVELOPMENT AND SYNTHESIS OF NOVEL DOPO-MODIFIED EPOXY RESIN AND ITS GLASS AND SISAL-BASED 3D WOVEN FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for advanced materials in the construction industry has led to an increased focus on developing flame-retardant and mechanically robust composites. Epoxy resins, known for their excellent adhesive and mechanical properties, have become popular for matrix materials in fiber-reinforced composites. However, conventional epoxy resins are inherently flammable, which limits their applicability in high-temperature or fire-prone environments. This study addresses this limitation by developing and synthesizing a novel flame-retardant epoxy resin with modified 9,10-dihydro-9-oxa-10-phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide (DOPO). Modified DOPO epoxy resin was synthesized and utilized as a matrix for 3D woven glass and sisal fiber-reinforced composites to enhance their flame-retardant properties. The 3D woven structure of the composite was chosen to improve load-bearing capacity and impact resistance, addressing the limitations of conventional 2D woven or random fiber composites in structural applications. The development of 3D woven glass and sisal fiber reinforced composite was done by VARTM method. The developed resin was characterized by FTIR, ¹H NMR, and ³¹P NMR. The composites were comprehensively characterized to assess their thermal stability and mechanical properties. Flame retardant properties of the composites were determined by limiting oxygen index (LOI), vertical burning tests, and cone calorimetry. Tensile and flexural strength tests are employed to evaluate the changes after modification. The highest LOI value achieved was 29.4. Cone calorimetry analysis demonstrated significant improvement in flame retardancy. The mechanical properties exhibited a decline in both tensile and flexural strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composites (FRCs) are widely utilized in the construction, automotive, and aerospace sectors owing to their superior mechanical strength, high strength-to-weight ratio, and design flexibility. Epoxy resins, frequently used as matrix components in these composites, provide exceptional mechanical and chemical resistance qualities [1–5]. Nonetheless, their intrinsic flammability considerably restricts their applicability in contexts where fire safety is paramount.

Inorganic (e.g., magnesium hydroxide, boric acid) and organic (e.g., phosphorus- and silicon-based compounds) flame-retardant additives have been integrated into epoxy resins to address this issue [6,7].

Glass fiber-reinforced composites (GFRC) are extensively utilized for their superior strength and rigidity, whilst natural fibers such as sisal provide ecological advantages, economic viability, and moderate mechanical properties [8,9]. Nonetheless, both glass and sisal fiber composites exhibit inadequate flame resistance, especially when integrated with combustible epoxy matrix. Recent advancements in flame-retardant resins and additives have enhanced fire performance; nonetheless, issues persist in attaining uniform dispersion and preserving mechanical integrity [10–14].

The majority of fiber-reinforced composites (FRCs) are constructed from two-dimensional woven, stitched, or braided fabrics, frequently demonstrating constrained interlaminar strength and damage tolerance. Conversely, 3D woven fabric structures provide superior mechanical qualities, particularly in the thickness dimension, through the integration of binder yarns [15,16]. Although the benefits of 3D woven composites are recognized, few research have investigated their incorporation with flame-retardant epoxy matrices.

This study fills the research gap by synthesizing novel DOPO-modified epoxy resin and employing it as a matrix for 3D woven glass and sisal fiber-reinforced composites. The main aim is to assess the flame-retardant and mechanical characteristics of the developed composites. Characterization encompasses Limiting Oxygen Index (LOI), vertical burning assessments (UL-94), cone calorimetry, and tensile and flexural strength evaluations to determine the efficacy of the DOPO alteration and the composite structure for high-performance, fire-resistant applications.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

9,10-Dihydro-9-oxa-10-phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide (DOPO), terephthalaldehyde (TDCA) was purchased by TCI India Pvt Ltd. E-Glass roving of 900 Tex was procured from Owens Corning (India) Private Limited. Sisal yarn of 1000 Tex was purchased from Dinesh Industries, Jaipur, India. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) was obtained from Atul Industries Ltd., India.

2.2 Synthesis of resin

0.1 mole (13.41 gram) of terephthalaldehyde (benzene-1,4-dicarbaldehyde) and 0.2 mole of DOPO (43.24 gram) were added in dry toluene of 250 mL in a three-necked flask under a nitrogen environment. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 h at 100°C. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. It was filtered and washed with toluene. The obtained solid was dried at 70°C in an oven. The synthesized compound (modified DOPO) was confirmed by FTIR and NMR spectra.

FTIR (cm^{-1}): OH stretching (3240 cm^{-1}), C=H stretching (2860 cm^{-1}), C-H stretching (2820 cm^{-1}), C=C stretching (1590 cm^{-1}), C-H scissoring (1430 cm^{-1}), P=O stretching (1120 cm^{-1}), C-H rocking vibration (713 cm^{-1}).

^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , ppm): 5.10–5.45 (m, 2H), 7.62 (m, 1H), 7.78–7.90 (m, 2H), 8.04 (m, 1H), 8.10–8.33 (m, 4H).

^{13}C NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , ppm): 120.02, 124.00, 124.76, 124.94, 125.89, 127.02, 127.46, 131.17, 134.17, 136.68, 154.40

^{31}P NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , ppm): 31.19.

DGEBA and modified DOPO were mixed in a molar ratio of 1:1 and heated up to 135°C. The reaction was carried out until a homogeneous solution was obtained for 45–55 min. Fig 1 depicts the synthesis scheme of the product. The reaction between DGEBA and modified DOPO is illustrated in Fig 1. The trap air was removed from the mixture under vacuum for 5 min. The resin was directly used for making composites.

Figure 1: Synthesis of modified resin

2.3 Characterizations

FTIR spectra were obtained at wavenumber ranges of 400–4000 cm^{-1} using Nicolet iS50 FTIR spectrophotometer. All NMR spectra were performed on a Bruker 500 NMR spectrometer (500 MHz) using DMSO- d_6 as solvent.

2.4 Development of fiber-reinforced modified epoxy resin-based composites

A four-layer 3D orthogonal fabric of glass and sisal fiber was developed in the customized rapier loom. Vacuum-assisted resin infusion (VARI) method was used to prepare composite materials [17]. The curing process was performed at ambient temperature for 8 h.

2.5 Measurement of flame-retardant properties of composites

The flammability of all the samples was determined using the limited oxygen index (LOI), according to ASTM D2863. Vertical flammability test was conducted according to the UL-94 standard. The cone calorimetry test was done according to the ASTM E1354.

2.6 Evaluation of mechanical properties of composites

According to ASTM D3039 and ASTM D7264, tensile strength and flexural rigidity were obtained.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterization of intermediate and resins

Fig 2 indicates the FTIR spectra of modified DOPO. The FTIR spectra showed the bands of OH stretching (3240 cm^{-1}), C-H stretching (2860 cm^{-1}), C-H stretching (2820 cm^{-1}), C=C stretching (1590 cm^{-1}), C-H scissoring (1430 cm^{-1}), P=O stretching (1120 cm^{-1}), C-H rocking vibration (713 cm^{-1}).

This suggested the formation of modified DOPO.

Figure 2: FTIR spectra of modified DOPO

^1H NMR spectra of modified DOPO are recorded in Fig 3. Types of A and B hydrogen showed multiplet in the 5.10-5.45 ppm region. Aromatic hydrogen showed various peaks: 7.62 (multiplet for one hydrogen), 7.78-7.90 (multiplet for two hydrogen), 8.04 (multiplet for one hydrogen), and 8.10-8.33 (multiplet for four hydrogen). Thus, it confirms the chemical structure.

Figure 3: ^1H NMR spectra of modified DOPO

¹³C NMR spectra of modified DOPO are recorded in Fig 4. Various carbon atom peaks were obtained at 120.02, 124.00, 124.76, 124.94, 125.89, 127.02, 127.46, 131.17, 134.17, 136.68, 154.40. As confirmed by ¹³C NMR, the presence of various carbons suggested the chemical structure of modified DOPO.

Figure 4: ¹³C NMR spectra of modified DOPO

³¹P NMR spectra of modified DOPO are depicted in Fig 5. One peak at 31.19 ppm was obtained due to one type of phosphorous atom attached to direct oxygen. Thus, FTIR and NMR spectra confirm the successful synthesis of modified DOPO.

Figure 5: ³¹P NMR spectra of modified DOPO

3.2 Flame retardant properties of composites

LOI (%) values of epoxy resin and modified epoxy resin-based glass and sisal fiber-reinforced composites are shown in Fig 6. EP stands for neat epoxy resin; MEP indicates modified epoxy resin. The LOI (%) value was observed in the neat epoxy resin-based glass (EP-GC) and sisal fiber (EP-SC) composite, which was 22.5 and 22.8, respectively. After the modification in epoxy resin, the LOI (%) value of glass and sisal fiber composite became 29.4 and 28.6. The results show a significant improvement in the limiting oxygen index. This proves the efficiency of modified resin to protect composites from flames.

Figure 6: LOI value of neat and modified epoxy resin composite

The vertical burning test of composites is shown in Table 1. Results indicate that after the modification, the rating of composites has improved. The results demonstrate a significant improvement in the rating of vertical flammability, confirming the modified resin's effectiveness in enhancing the composites' flame resistance.

Table 1: UL 94 rating of composites

COMPOSITE SAMPLES	UL-94 TEST RATING	SIGNIFICANCE
EP-GC	NR	No rating
MEP-GC	V2	Burning stop in 30 seconds
EP-SC	NR	No rating
MEP-SC	V2	Burning stop in 30 seconds

3.3 Cone Calorimetry Test

Neat epoxy glass exhibits the highest peak heat release rate (pHRR) of 390.2 kW/m². After the modification, the pHRR value of the epoxy glass composite was 275.69 kW/m². The same patterns are

shown in the case of epoxy sisal and modified epoxy sisal composites (Fig 8), which exhibit 897.43 and 767.57 kW/m² respectively. Using the modified epoxy resin, a 29.3% reduction in the peak heat release rate was achieved with glass fiber, while a 14.47% reduction was observed with sisal fiber. These variations are attributed to the interaction between the resin and fibers and the distribution of the resin within the fiber matrix. Moreover, the modified resin exhibits an early release phenomenon (at a shorter time), which is attributed to the decomposition of flame-retardant moieties such as P=O, thereby protecting the composite from further burning.

Glass fiber is inherently flame-retardant; however, incorporating a neat flammable resin renders the composite flammable. The synthesized resin significantly enhances the flame-retardant properties of glass fiber-based composites, effectively making them inherently flame-retardant.

On the other hand, sisal is highly flammable. In this case, the developed resin protects the fiber and the entire composite, reducing its flammability. In conclusion, modifying the resin with phosphorus-containing groups imparts flame-retardant protection to the composites.

Figure 7: HRR value of neat and modified epoxy resin composite

Figure 8: (Left) modified epoxy glass composite and (Right) modified epoxy sisal glass composite

3.6 Mechanical Properties of Composites

The tensile properties and flexural rigidity of neat and modified epoxy glass and sisal fiber-reinforced composites are presented in Figs 10 and 11. The curves in these figures show that the tensile and flexural properties of the modified composites are inferior to those of neat epoxy after incorporating modified DOPO into the epoxy resins. This decline in mechanical performance aligns with reported studies, which suggested that a high concentration of phosphorus-containing flame retardants often has a detrimental impact on the mechanical characteristics of the polymer matrix [18,19].

Figure 9: Tensile strength of composites

Figure 10: Flexural rigidity of composites

4. CONCLUSION

A novel DOPO-modified epoxy resin was successfully synthesized, and ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, and ³¹P NMR confirmed its chemical structure. The high phosphorus content of the modified resin imparted excellent flame retardancy to epoxy resins. The LOI value of composites was increased from 21 to 29 and UL-94 test rating was improved from no rating to V-2 rating. The significant decrement of 30% s in case of glass and almost 15% in sisal shown in peak heat release rate. Using a 3D woven fiber architecture further contributed to improved structural performance, particularly in load-bearing and impact resistance. However, the integration of the flame-retardant additive resulted in a reduction in mechanical properties, including tensile and flexural strength. Overall, the study demonstrates a promising approach to enhancing fire safety in fiber-reinforced composites for construction and structural applications, highlighting the need to balance flame retardancy with mechanical performance. This work provides a novel route for developing efficient flame-retardant composites for high-performance materials for construction, automotive, and aerospace applications.

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